

Synthetic and antifungal studies of some novel alkylidenamidothiophosphoric esters

Vijaya Kabra*, Neelima Gupta and Ritu Mathur

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, India

E-mail : kabrasg@hotmail.com, neelima@sancharnet.in

Manuscript received 11 June 2002, revised 23 July 2003, accepted 21 October 2003

Phosphorylation of *N*-alkylcycloiminium halides of two important *N*-heterocycles, namely thiazole and benzothiazole has been accomplished with phosphorus trichloride in presence of a base. The intermediate aminodichlorophosphines thus generated *in situ* undergo nucleophilic substitution and oxidation reaction to yield eleven new alkylidenamidothiophosphoric esters, which have been screened for their fungitoxic activity.

Organophosphoric esters and related compounds are well known for their broad spectrum biocidal activity and superiority to organochlorine pesticides¹. Halophosphines have been used widely as versatile starting materials for the synthesis of variety of organophosphorus derivatives². Aminohalophosphines incorporating *N*-heterocyclic ring have become accessible recently by a facile synthetic route³. In the present communication, we report the synthesis of title compounds incorporating thiazole or benzothiazole ring through the intermediacy of the corresponding aminohalophosphines. Resulting thiophosphoric esters have been tested for their fungitoxic properties.

Results and discussion

N-Alkyl-2-aminothiazolium/benzothiazolium halides **1** on reaction with equimolar amount of phosphorus trichlo-

ride in the presence of two-fold amount of triethylamine in methylene chloride resulted in the formation of the corresponding aminohalophosphines **2**, which were subsequently subjected to nucleophilic substitution with diethylamine or *o/p*-cresol accompanied with oxidation with sulfur. In this manner, eleven new representatives of two series of alkylidenamidothiophosphoric esters, namely (3-alkyl-2-thiazol/benzothiazolyldenamido)bis-(diethylamido)thiophosphates **3** and (3-alkyl-2-thiazol/benzothiazolyldenamido)bis(*O*-2/4-methylphenyl)-thiophosphates **4** were obtained (Scheme 1).

All the products (**3,4**) are new crystalline stable solids and have been characterized by the downfield ³¹P NMR signal at δ 59–78 in the expected range of tetra coordinated phosphorus⁴. In the ¹H NMR spectra of **3a, 3c, 4a**

Scheme 1

Table 1. Fungicidal activity of the compounds 3, 4

Compds.	Average radial growth in mm			
	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>		<i>Alternaria cymopsidies</i>	
	100 ppm	500 ppm	100 ppm	500 ppm
3a	70.83 (70.0–72.5)	50.00 (45.0–52.5)	65.83 (62.5–67.5)	62.5 (57.5–70.0)
3b	30.00 (22.5–36.0)	24.00 (20.0–30.0)	13.67 (12.5–15.0)	0.00 (nil)
3c	78.33 (70.0–85.0)	76.67 (70.0–80.0)	81.67 (80.0–85.0)	74.17 (70.0–77.5)
4a	65.83 (60.0–75.0)	62.73 (60.0–67.5)	72.50 (70.0–75.0)	70.83 (62.5–85.0)
4b	65.83 (60.0–70.0)	17.67 (14.5–20.0)	77.50 (75.0–80.0)	14.17 (10.0–20.0)
Control with solvent	80.00 (75.0–85.0)	80.00 (75.0–85.0)	84.17 (77.5–90.0)	84.17 (77.5–90.0)
Control	82.50 (85.0–87.0)	84.17 (80.0–87.5)	85.00 (80.0–90.0)	85.00 (80.0–90.0)
Gen. mean	67.62	56.46	68.62	55.83
S.Em.±	3.40	2.63	2.13	3.79
C.D.5%	10.32	7.97	6.46	11.50
C.V.%	8.71	8.06	5.38	11.77

and **4b**, H-4 and H-5 protons of the thiazole ring show long range coupling ($^5J_{P,H}$ 1.4–2.8 Hz) with phosphorus. It is interesting to note that in the case of **3a**, the NCH_2 protons of diethylamino moiety are diastereotopic and give two sets of *ddq* at δ 3.12 and 3.22 due to the coupling with phosphorus in addition to the *vicinal* and *geminal* couplings. In the case of **1d**, the product obtained from the reaction with *p*-cresol and sulfur was found to be a mixture of disubstituted **4d** (δ ^{31}P 77.7) and monosubstituted **4d'** (δ ^{31}P 80.6) compounds; however, from the reaction with *o*-cresol and sulfur only monosubstituted product **4g'** (δ ^{31}P 79.6) was obtained probably due to steric reasons.

Bioactivity :

Compounds **3a,b,c** and **4a,b** were screened for fungitoxic activity against *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Alternaria cymopsidies* from cumin (*cuminum cyminum*) and clusterbean (*cymopsis tetragonal*), respectively by adopting food poisoning technique. The results in terms of radial growth in mm along with the statistical analysis of the data have been presented in Table 1. The test samples have been tested at 100 and 500 ppm concentrations and compared with the solvent control. The potato dextrose agar nutrient medium was poisoned with test compound and using three replica sets radial growth was measured to evaluate their fungitoxic activity. All the compounds except compound **3c** were found to be significantly active against both the fungi. **3b** was found to be most effective in reducing the radial growth of the mycelium at both concentrations and in the case of *Alternaria cymopsidies*, zero radial growth was observed. At higher concentration, **4b** was found to be as effective as **3b** in

reducing the radial growth of *Fusarium oxysporum*. These observations reveal that a bulky *N*-alkyl substituent ($N-CH_2C_6H_4CH_3$) in **3b** and **4b** enhances the fungitoxic activity for each fungi, in confirmity with the earlier results reported in the literature⁵. Also, trisamidothiophosphates **3** have been found to show stronger fungicidal activity than amidodiarylthiophosphates **4**.

Experimental

All the commercial reagents and solvents were dried and distilled by common methods before use. M.ps. were determined by capillary method and are uncorrected. All operations involving phosphorus compounds were carried out in dry equipment under nitrogen atmosphere. NMR spectra were recorded on Jeol FX 90Q (1H NMR at 89.55 MHz, ^{31}P NMR at 36.23 MHz) or Bruker Spectrospin DPX 300 (1H NMR at 300.13 MHz, ^{31}P NMR at 121.49 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal or 85% H_3PO_4 as external standard.

3-Alkyl-2-aminothiazol/benzothiazolium halides (1) :
General procedure : To a solution of 2-aminothiazole/benzothiazole (0.04 mol) in tetrahydrofuran (40 ml) was added an equimolar amount of substituted methyl bromide/iodide and stirring was continued for 10 to 12 days at RT. White to brown coloured solid thus separated was filtered and dried. In the case of **1b** and **1e**, solid was obtained by refluxing the reaction mixture in acetone (40 ml) for 45–50 h. **1a** (57%); m.p. 110–112°; δ 1H (DMSO- d_6) 1.39 (3H, t, $^3J_{H,H}$ 7.3 Hz, NCH_2CH_3), 4.15 (2H, q, $^3J_{H,H}$ 7.3 Hz, NCH_2), ϵ .89 (1H, d, $^3J_{H,H}$ 4.6 Hz, H-5), 7.31 (1H, d, $^3J_{H,H}$ 4.6 Hz, H-4), 9.41 (2H, s, NH_2). **1b** (87%); 220–221°; δ 1H (DMSO- d_6) 2.29 (3H, s, CH_3),

5.27 (2H, s, NCH₂), 6.61 (1H, d, ³J_{H,H} 4.8 Hz, H-5), 6.70 (1H, d, ³J_{H,H} 4.8 Hz, H-4), 7.11 (4H, s, C₆H₄), 9.21 (2H, s, NH₂). **1c** (96%); 183–185° (Found : C, 19.91; H, 2.97; N, 11.10. C₄H₇N₂S requires : C, 19.84; H, 2.91; N, 11.60%); δ ¹H (DMSO-*d*₆) 3.58 (3H, s, NCH₃), 6.58 (1H, d, ³J_{H,H} 4.3 Hz, H-5), 7.04 (1H, d, ³J_{H,H} 4.3 Hz, H-4), 9.05 (2H, s, NH₂). **1d** (72%); 206–208°; δ ¹H (DMSO-*d*₆) 4.02 (3H, s, NCH₃), 7.47–7.78 (4H, m, ArH), 10.21 (2H, s, NH₂). **1e** (72%); 208–210°; δ ¹H (DMSO-*d*₆) 1.32 (3H, t, ³J_{H,H} 7.0 Hz, NCH₂CH₃), 4.32 (2H, q, ³J_{H,H} 7.0 Hz, NCH₂), 7.41 (1H, t, ³J_{H,H} 7.6 Hz, H-7), 7.57 (1H, t, ³J_{H,H} 7.5 Hz, H-6), 7.70 (1H, d, ³J_{H,H} 8.2 Hz, H-8), 7.99 (1H, d, ³J_{H,H} 8.0 Hz, H-5), 10.01 (2H, s, NH₂). **1f** (58%); 228–229°; δ ¹H (DMSO-*d*₆) 5.63 (2H, s, NCH₂), 7.01–7.77 (9H, m, ArH), 10.41 (2H, s, NH₂).

(3-Alkyl-2-thiazol/benzothiazolylidenamido)bis (diethylamido)thiophosphates (**3**) : *General procedure* : To a well stirred suspension of 3-alkyl-2-aminothiazol/benzothiazolium halide (0.01 mol) in methylene chloride (15ml) at 0–5° was added phosphorus trichloride (0.01 mol) followed by dropwise addition of a solution of triethylamine (0.02 mol) in methylene chloride (20 ml). After 5–20 h of stirring at RT, a solution of diethylamine (0.04 mol) in methylene chloride was added to the reaction mixture followed by sulfur (0.01 mol). Stirring was continued for 20–24 h; the solvent was thereafter removed under reduced pressure and the residue extracted with diethyl ether (2 × 50 ml). The combined ethereal extracts were concentrated and left in refrigerator, whereupon colourless to pale yellow crystals deposited, which were filtered and dried. **3a** syrupy mass; δ ³¹P 67.8; δ ¹H (CDCl₃) 1.08 (12H, t, ³J_{H,H} 7.1, PNCH₂CH₃), 1.30 (3H, t, ³J_{H,H} 7.1, NCH₂CH₃), 3.12 (4H, ddq, ²J_{H,H} 14.2, ³J_{P,H} 12.2, ³J_{H,H} 7.1, PNCH₂), 3.22 (4H, ddq, ²J_{H,H} 14.2, ³J_{P,H} 12.2, ³J_{H,H} 7.1, PNCH₂), 3.87 (2H, q, ³J_{H,H} 7.3, NCH₂), 6.24 (1H, dd, ³J_{H,H} 4.9, ⁵J_{P,H} 1.4, H-5), 6.71 (1H, dd, ³J_{H,H} 4.9, ⁵J_{P,H} 2.2, H-4). **3b** (65%); m.p. 78–80° (Found : C, 55.85; H, 7.76; N, 13.55. C₁₉H₃₁N₄S₂P requires : C, 55.66; H, 7.62; N, 13.67%); δ ³¹P 65.8; δ ¹H (CDCl₃) 1.02 (12H, t, ³J_{H,H} 7.1, NCH₂CH₃), 2.29 (3H, s, C₆H₄CH₃), 3.12 (8H, dq, ³J_{P,H} 12.2, ³J_{H,H} 7.1, NCH₂CH₃), 4.89 (2H, s, NCH₂), 6.14 (1H, d, ³J_{H,H} 5.7, H-5), 6.51 (1H, d, ³J_{H,H} 5.7, H-4), 7.03 (4H, s, C₆H₄). **3c** (60%); 52–53°; δ ³¹P 65.7; δ ¹H (CDCl₃) 1.11 (12H, t, ³J_{H,H} 8.5, NCH₂CH₃), 3.16 (8H, dq, ³J_{P,H} 12.8, ³J_{H,H} 7.1, NCH₂), 3.40 (3H, s, NCH₃), 6.21 (1H, dd, ³J_{H,H} 5.6, ⁵J_{P,H} 2.0, H-5), 6.69 (1H, dd, ³J_{H,H} 5.6, ⁵J_{P,H} 2.8, H-4). **3d** (63%); 60–61°; δ ³¹P 65.7; δ ¹H (CDCl₃) 1.08 (12H, t, ³J_{H,H} 7.1, NCH₂CH₃), 3.13 (8H, dq, ³J_{P,H} 12.7, ³J_{H,H}

7.1, NCH₂CH₃), 3.5 (3H, s, NCH₃), 7.06–7.57 (4H, m, ArH).

(3-Alkyl-2-thiazol/benzothiazolylidenamido)bis (O-2/4-methylphenyl)thiophosphates (**4**) : *General procedure* : A procedure similar to that for **3** was followed using triethylamine (0.02 mol) and a solution of *o/p*-cresol (0.02 mol) in methylene chloride (10 ml) in place of diethylamine when pale yellow crystals of **4** were obtained. **4a** (73%); m.p. 82–84° (Found : C, 56.13; H, 5.09; N, 6.70. C₁₉H₂₁N₂O₂S₂P requires : C, 56.42; H, 5.23; N, 6.92%); δ ³¹P 58.7; δ ¹H (CDCl₃) 1.20 (3H, t, ³J_{H,H} 8.5, NCH₂CH₃), 2.31 (6H, s, OC₆H₄CH₃), 3.89 (2H, q, ³J_{H,H} 8.5, NCH₂CH₃), 6.46 (1H, dd, ³J_{H,H} 5.7, ⁵J_{P,H} 2.1, H-5), 6.81 (1H, dd, ³J_{H,H} 5.7, ⁵J_{P,H} 2.8, H-4), 7.26–7.32 (8H, m, OC₆H₄). **4b** (58%); 90–92° (Found : C, 61.92; H, 5.17; N, 5.60. C₂₅H₂₅N₂O₂S₂P requires : C, 62.48; H, 5.24; N, 5.82%); δ ³¹P 59.6; δ ¹H (CDCl₃) 2.30 (3H, s, CH₂C₆H₄CH₃), 2.32 (6H, s, OC₆H₄CH₃), 4.89 (2H, s, NCH₂), 6.21 (1H, dd, ³J_{H,H} 5.6, ⁵J_{P,H} 1.4, H-5), 6.52 (1H, dd, ³J_{H,H} 5.6, ⁵J_{P,H} 2.8, H-4), 7.16 (12H, s, ArH). **4d + 4d'** {**4d** (72%); δ ³¹P 77.7; δ ¹H (CDCl₃) 2.29 (6H, s, OC₆H₄CH₃), 3.55 (3H, s, NCH₃), 7.08–7.54 (12H, m, ArH)} + {**4d'** (28%); δ ³¹P 80.6; δ ¹H 2.32 (6H, s, OC₆H₄CH₃), 3.61 (3H, s, NCH₃), 7.08–7.54 (8H, m, ArH)}. **4e** (69%); 80–83°; δ ³¹P 76.6; δ ¹H (CDCl₃) 1.14 (3H, t, ³J_{H,H} 7.2, NCH₂CH₃), 2.17 (6H, s, OC₆H₄CH₃), 4.36 (2H, q, ³J_{H,H} 7.2, NCH₂), 7.21–7.51 (12H, m, ArH). **4f** (59%); 110–112°; δ ³¹P 77.4; δ ¹H (CDCl₃) 2.27 (6H, s, OC₆H₄CH₃), 5.29 (2H, s, NCH₂), 7.04 (4H, d, ³J_{H,H} 8.3, *m*-H), 7.02–7.16 (6H, m, H-5, H-6, *o*-H), 7.19 (1H, d, ³J_{H,H} 7.5, H-7), 7.25 (5H, s, CH₂C₆H₅), 7.49 (1H, d, ³J_{H,H} 7.5, H-4). **4g'** (64%); 90–92°; δ ³¹P 79.6; δ ¹H (CDCl₃) 2.43 (3H, s, OC₆H₄CH₃), 3.63 (3H, s, NCH₃), 7.14 (1H, d, ³J_{H,H} 7.2, H-7), 7.19 (1H, d, ³J_{H,H} 7.2, H-4), 7.22–7.47 (5H, m, H-5, H-6, *p*-H, *m*-H), 7.60 (1H, d, ³J_{H,H} 7.8, *o*-H). **4h** (65%); 70–72°; δ ³¹P 76.6; δ ¹H (CDCl₃) 1.18 (3H, t, ³J_{H,H} 7.2, NCH₂CH₃), 2.33 (6H, s, OC₆H₄CH₃), 4.09 (2H, q, ³J_{H,H} 7.2, NCH₂), 7.01–7.52 (12H, m, ArH).

Acknowledgement

Financial support from the C.S.I.R., New Delhi is gratefully acknowledged. Thanks are due to R.S.I.C., Lucknow for providing mass and NMR spectra and A.R.S., Durgapura, Jaipur for providing facilities for investigation of fungicidal activity.

References

- (a) H. C. L. Gupta, "Insecticides : Toxicology and Uses", Agrotech Publishing Academy Press, Udaipur, 1999, p. 51.

Note

- 211; (b) S. Cunningham, "Environmental Science of Global Concern", 3rd. ed., C. Brown Publishers, 1995, p. 243; (c) F. Matsumara, "Toxicology of Insecticides", 2nd. ed., Plenum Press, New York, 1985, p. 62; (d) S. Walia and B. S. Parmar, "Pesticides, Crop protection and Environment", Oxford, IBH, New Delhi, 1995.
2. (a) J. I. G. Cadogan and P. K. G. Hodgson, *Phosphorus Sulfur*, 1987, **30**, 3; (b) M. Regitz, "Organische Phosphor-Verbindungen", in 'Houben Weyl-Methoden der Organischen Chemie', Thieme Stuttgart, New York, 1982, Vol. E1 and E2.
3. (a) R. K. Bansal, R. Mahnot and D. C. Sharma, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1991, **32**, 6433; (b) K. Karaghiosoff, R. K. Bansal and N. Gupta, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1992, **47**, 373.
4. J. C. Tebby, "Phosphorus-31 NMR Spectroscopy in Stereochemical Analysis", Vol. 8, eds. J. G. Verkade and L. D. Quin, VCH, U.S.A., 1987, p. 1.
5. (a) R. L. Metcalf in "Advances in Pest Control Research", Interscience Publishers, Inc, New York, 1957; (b) R. J. Brauer, *J. Pharmacol. Exptl. Therap.*, 1948, **92**, 162; (c) A. Toy, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 2065.